

Heterocyclic Fungicides—Part II

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A number of 5-pyrazolone and 6-isoxazolone compounds have shown good fungicidal action against *Helminthosporium oryzae*. The phenyl group, cyclopropane ring, and 5-isoxazolone ring confer potency. Chemicals, which are quite effective against *Pyricularia oryzae* are less effective against *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

THE disease caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* is known as the brown leaf spot. It is one of the worst diseases of rice. Under certain peculiar combination of weather factors, epidemic causing total destruction of crops occur. Two such epidemics have occurred in India.

Amongst the fungicides in use for controlling this infection organo-mercurials were found to be most suitable. After the finding that the residual mercury left on the plant is absorbed by the cattle fed on it and the metal is finally transmitted to the human beings through milk and meat, use of organo-mercurials has been restricted.

It was found in course of this investigation that *Helminthosporium oryzae* was more resistant to the chemicals tested; some of the chemicals which are effective against *Pyricularia oryzae* are ineffective against *Helminthosporium oryzae* even at 5000 parts per million. In the following tables are listed compounds which show significant action against *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

For our investigation, the mercuric fungicide (i.e. compound no. 11) was taken as a standard. Another compound, Aureofungin, which is an antibiotic is also applied in the field and found to have same effectiveness as compound no. 11. From the observations on compounds 3,4 and 5, it is seen that a phenyl or an acid

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	M.P. (°C)	Conc. in parts per million.	% of inhibition of spore germination
1.	Ph	Me	H	H	128	5000	78
2.	-CONH ₂	Me	H	H	184	5000	75
3.	Ph	Me	-NO	H	157	1000	92
4.	-CONH ₂	Me	-NO	H	220	5000	92
5.	H	Me	-NO	H	231	5000	79
6.	Ph	Me	Br	Br	65	1000	92

TABLE 2

Sl. no.	Name of the compounds	M.P. (°C)	Conc. in parts per million.	% of inhibition of spore germination.
7.	Aza-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone ¹)	181	1000	92
8.	Aza-bis-(3-methyl-5-pyrazolone ²)	238*	5000	Ineffective
9.	3-Methyl-4-benzilidene-5-isoxazolone	146	1000	95
10.	4, 4'-Benzylidene-bis-(1-amido-3-methyl 5-pyrazolone)	204	5000	85
11.	Mercuric derivative of fury lidene-chalkone.	136	50	94

* decomposition.

TABLE 3

Sl. no.	Name	M.P. (°C)	Conc. in parts per million.	% of inhibition of spore germination
12.	[(1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-pyrazolin-4-yl) (3-methyl-5-oxo-2-isoxazolin-4-yl) (phenyl)]methane.	155	5000	89
13.	[(Spiro-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-isoxazolin-4-yl) (spiro-1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-pyrazolin-4-yl) (phenyl)] cyclopropane.	110	500	93
14.	[Spiro-bis-(1-amido-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-pyrazolin-4-yl)-(phenyl)] cyclopropane.	110	500	97

amide substituent on the nitrogen in number one position of the pyrazolone ring confers best activity amongst the nitrosopyrazolones. Similar efficacy of the phenyl substituent on the nitrogen in number one position is shown from the study of serials 7 and 8. From the comparison of action of compounds 12 and 13, it can be inferred that formation of a cyclopropane ring promotes activity. The potency of 5-isoxazolone ring is shown by the efficacy of compounds 9, 12 and 13. In the case of *Helminthosporium oryzae*, compounds serial 5, 14 and 13 have the peculiar property of shrivelling the cell of the spore and in a few cases the spores were seen to be completely empty. A similar property has been reported³ of compounds causing broken spores of *Alternaria solani*. These compounds were thiones and thiocarbamates. But so far no report has been made of pyrazolone derivatives having this effect.

Experimental

Compounds serial 1 to 5 and 9 were prepared according to the published methods^{4,5}.

Preparation of 1-phenyl-3-ethyl-4,4-dibromo-5-pyrazolone, Serial no. 6.

1-Phenyl-3 methyl-5-pyrazolone (2g) was dissolved in minimum amount of glacial acetic acid at room temperature. To this solution, bromine in acetic acid (bromine 2 ml+8ml acetic acid) was added dropwise till the bromine colour persisted, on shaking. It was allowed to stand for one hour and water (about 50 ml) was added to it. Yellow precipitate came out immediately. Sometimes a yellow oil remains, but on standing and shaking, it becomes a solid compound. It was then filtered and washed with water, found m.p. 65°. The compound on exposure to light loses excess of bromine, and becomes green. Recrystallisation of the compound was tried from 1 : 1 acetic acid but it was converted to black oil.

Preparation of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(1-amido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone), Sl. no. 10.

1-Amido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (2g) was dissolved in minimum glacial acetic acid with the aid of a hot water bath. Freshly distilled benzaldehyde (2.8 ml) was added to the above solution. It was then well shaken and set aside for 24 hrs. The solution was then diluted with water when a pinkish brown precipitate was

obtained. It was set aside for 1 hr. It was filtered and washed with water, m.p. 204°, yield 1.5 g.

Preparation of mercuric derivative of Furylidene chalkone, Sl. no. 11.

The liquid, furylidene chalkone (about 2 ml) was added to a saturated acetone solution (10 ml) of mercuric chloride. It was allowed to stand over night, Needle shaped crystals were obtained, the solution was filtered and the crystalline precipitate washed with a little acetone. On allowing the filtrate to stand for a longer time another crop of crystals was obtained, m.p. of both crops -136°, yield -1.5g.

Preparation of [(1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-pyrazoline-4-yl) (3-methyl-5-oxo-isoxazolin-4-yl) phenyl] methane, Sl. no. 12.

3-Methyl-4-benzylidene-5-isoxazolone (2 g.) was dissolved in minimum amount of absolute alcohol, by refluxing on a hot water bath. 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (2g) was dissolved in minimum 2N NaOH and added to the above solution. The mixture was then refluxed for 45 minutes and allowed to cool and settle overnight. It was then neutralised by dilute hydrochloric acid. A brown precipitate separated out, which was at first a little gummy. The precipitate was washed with water, and then with a little alcohol, m.p. 65°, yield 15g.

Preparation of [3-methyl-5-oxo-2-isoxazolin-4-yl) (1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-pyrazolin-4-yl) - spirane-2-phenyl]-cyclopropane, Sl. no. 13.

The above compound (2g) was dissolved in about 10ml of 20% NaOH solution (at room temperature). A saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide was prepared. The alkali solution was stirred by a magnetic stirrer and the iodine solution was added till the colour of iodine persisted. It was stirred for 5 minutes more and then allowed to settle down. The deep-brown precipitate obtained was washed 3 to 4 times with sulphurous acid solution and then finally with water, m.p. 110°, yield 1g.

Preparation of [bis-spiro-(1-amido-3-methyl-5-oxo-2-pyrazolin-4-yl) phenyl] cyclopropane, Sl. no. 14.

4,4'-Benzylidene-bis-(1-amido-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (3 g) was dissolved in about 10 ml of 20% NaOH

solution at room temperature. The solution was stirred continuously by a magnetic stirrer while the saturated solution of I₂ in Potassium iodide was added dropwise till the iodine colour persisted, the stirring was continued for 5 minutes more and then the reaction mixture set aside for half an hour. A deep brown precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed thrice with aqueous solution of sodium thiosulphate, (or sulphurous acid) and then with distilled water, m. p. 100°, yield-2.5 g.

TABLE-4

Sl. no. in Tables.	Dilution in parts per million.	Time of contact 24 hours Inhibition in test slide (%)	Inhibition in control slide (%)
1	1000	14	8
	2500	62	8
	5000	86	8
2	1000	13	8
	2500	50	8
	5000	83	8
3	1000	100	8
	2500	100	8
	5000	100	8
4	1000	15	5
	2500	51	5
	5000	97	5
5	1000	11	7
	2500	50	7
	5000	86	7
6	250	34	8
	500	91	8
	1000	100	8
7	250	14	8
	500	97	8
	1000	100	8
8	5'00	Ineffective	
9	250	14	5
	500	70	5
	1000	100	5
10	1000	48	7
	2500	60	7
	5000	92	7
11	10	20	6
	25	28	6
	50	100	6
12	1000	35	11
	2500	100	11
	5000	100	11
13	100	11	5
	250	57	5
	500	98	5
14	100	98	3
	250	100	3
	500	100	3

Procedure for fungicidal assay : The preparation of stock solution for each chemical was the same as it was in tests against *Pyricularia oryzae* described in Part-I of this investigation⁴. In this investigation, the chemicals were tested against the fungus *Helminthosporium oryzae*. *Helminthosporium oryzae* is actually the imperfect, asexual, stage of the fungus *Cochliobolus miyabeanus*. It is found to affect the rice plant, only in its imperfect stage.

With test chemical serial no. 5, the spores which had germinated at 5000 ppm, had very short germ tubes. With serial no. 3, at and above 500 ppm, some of the spores which had not germinated were seen to be shrivelled and a few were empty. With serial no. 7, above 100 ppm, all the spores which had germinated had very short germ tubes. With serial 14 and 13, at and above 100 ppm, some of the spores were shrivelled up and some were quite empty ; at 50 ppm, and 100 ppm, spores which had germinated had very short germ tubes.

Serial no. 8, was found to be quite ineffective even at 5000 ppm against *Helminthosporium oryzae* although it was quite effective against *Pyricularia oryzae*.

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